

Brushless Synchronous Machine Field Winding Interturn Fault Severity Estimation Through Deep Neural Networks

Rubén Pascual, Kumar Mahtani, Eduardo Rivero, and Carlos A. Platero

Abstract—Interturn faults (ITF) at the main machine field winding in brushless synchronous machines (BSM) are not easy to detect as the scarcity of measurements in the rotor. This paper presents a new field winding ITF severity estimation technique based on deep learning algorithms. The theoretical exciter field current is calculated through an artificial neural network, from the machine output values, and then compared to the measured exciter field current. The estimation and the comparison are carried out without need of other than the machine electrical outputs and the exciter field current measurements. To verify the proposed technique, numerous healthy and faulty condition tests were performed on a special laboratory testbench, with more than 7 million measurements in healthy and more than 1 million in different faulty conditions. So as firstly to train the neural network with healthy operation datasets, and secondly to test its capability to estimate the fault severity level. The use of deep neural networks has proven to enhance the accuracy of the exciter field current estimation with respect to previous theoretical model-based methods, enabling to increase the sensitivity and the reliability of the fault detection and fault severity calculation.

Index Terms—AC machines, brushless machines, condition monitoring, deep learning, fault detection, fault diagnosis, generators, neural networks, power generation, synchronous machines.

I. INTRODUCTION

BRUSHLESS synchronous machines (BSM) are made up of an exciter and a main machine, which are mechanically coupled through a common shaft. The exciter is responsible for providing the required field power to the main machine. The exciter field winding is wound around the stator poles, while its armature is found on the rotor in the form of a three-phase winding. A rotating diode rectifier converts the AC output from

the exciter into the DC excitation input to the main machine. The main machine field winding is situated on the rotor, while its armature is arranged on the stator.

Different BSM excitation systems can be distinguished according to the source of the field power provided to the exciter [1], [2], notably self-excited systems either from the machine output (such as shunt-connected systems and excitation boost systems) or from stator auxiliary windings, systems employing a permanent magnet generator (PMG) as a pilot exciter, and systems resorting to external auxiliary power sources, eventually the auxiliary power systems in power plants. Moreover, asynchronous exciter systems [3] or even exciterless solutions [4] are nowadays trendy research lines.

Avoiding the use of brushes and slip rings is the main advantage of BSM, which enables to increase operational safety, especially in potentially explosive atmospheres, and to reduce maintenance requirements and costs.

Therefore, BSM are nowadays widely found in power generation applications ranging from kVA to MVA, for instance, in hydro- and pumped-hydro-storage power plants (hydro-generators [5]) and in nuclear power plants (turbo-generators [6]). Also, BSM cover other applications for which the speed of voltage regulation is not a stringent requirement, but safety is, such as standby power supply and power generation in the oil and gas and in the marine industries.

In all the cases, BSM shall comply with reliability standards commonly required in industry. In this context, the requirements regarding protection against faults and abnormal operation conditions are major concerns [7], [8]. Because of these requirements and also because these machines are one of the most valuable assets in power systems, complex protection systems based on multifunctional digital relaying are usual.

Due to the electrical, thermal, ambient and mechanical stresses involved in the energy conversion process, BSM are subjected to various types of faults. In this paper, interturn faults (ITF) at the main machine field winding will be tackled.

These are prominent electrical faults [9] in a rotating element to which direct access is unattainable. The fault severity level is directly proportional to the number of shorted turns with respect to the total turns [10], [11].

Rotor ITF are not easy to detect, because no large over-currents are usually derived. Indeed, if the fault severity is

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below a certain tolerable level, the machine can pursue its operation. Nevertheless, magnetic unbalance would provoke additional mechanical stress which could lead to further condition worsening.

Generally, insulation weakening [12], [13], [14] is considered to be at the origin of ITF. The high stresses applied on the insulation can lead to its deterioration and eventually encourage a turn-to-turn short-circuit in the weakened area.

One of the most significant electrical stresses applied to the field winding insulation is caused by the voltage spikes produced by the rectifying diodes during commutation. Moreover, in case of some electromagnetic transient as pole slip, the rotor is affected by important dielectric stress.

The high stresses applied on the rotor insulation are not only related to electric potential differences, but also to mechanical stresses due to vibrations and frictions that can gradually erode the insulating material and to thermal stresses due to temperature spikes. In fact, a local increase in temperature, for instance as a result of a manufacturing defect, can lead to a rapid deterioration of the insulating layer between turns. Finally, ambient contamination with fine particles such as sand, salt or aerosols, or with liquids such as water or acids, can encourage ITF as well.

For rotor ITF detection and severity estimation in BSM, some previous model-based approaches [15], [16] employed the comparison between the theoretical model estimation obtained from the machine output values, i.e., the calculated exciter field current under healthy conditions, and the measured exciter field current, in order to attest deviations from the healthy condition and to compute the fault severity level from the relative difference between both values. This method works under the logic that in the case of an ITF, and in order to maintain the same machine output setpoint, the required field current will increase in proportion with the number of shorted turns, so that the magnetomotive force provided to the main machine remains unchanged.

The main objective of this work is to overcome an important limitation of these previous model-based methods, which is their sensitivity, within the same mentioned operating logic. The sensitivity is affected, on the one hand, by the measurement errors, and on the other hand, by the machine model errors, mainly due to parameter estimations [17] and characteristic curves procurement. The machine model errors are the ones that can be avoided through the use of machine learning. If the estimation of the theoretical excitation current under healthy conditions can be improved, then the sensitivity of the method will be lower so as to detect smaller ITF and to provide a more accurate value for the severity level.

For this purpose, this paper presents an improvement in the theoretical exciter field current estimation achieved by the use of deep neural network (DNN) algorithms. The proposed method has been built leaning on a special laboratory setup, firstly to train the DNN under healthy conditions and secondly to validate the model with different faulty condition tests with various severity levels.

First of all, this work provides a brief overview of the existing field winding ITF detection methods, as well as of some field current estimation techniques, in Section II. Afterwards, the

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF VARIOUS SIGNAL-BASED FAULT DETECTION METHODS

	CURRENT VOLTAGE	AIRGAP FLUX	STRAY FLUX
Accuracy	↓	↑	↓
No noise influence	↓	↑	↓
Computational simplicity	↓	↓	↓
Measurement range width	↓	↑	↑
No machine design constraints	↑	↓	↑
No installation constraints	↑	↓	↑
Low equipment cost	↑	↓	↓

foundations of the proposed methods are discussed in Section III. The methodology for the application of DNN to carry out the exciter field current prediction is presented in Section IV. Then, in Section V the experimental setup and the experimental tests performed on it, under ITF with different severity levels, are presented. The results of the proposed technique are put forward in Section VI. Finally, the conclusions of the work are enclosed in Section VII.

II. STATE OF THE ART

A. Field Winding ITF Online Detection Methods

Approaches to online [18] field winding ITF detection are mostly signal-based, consisting in processing electrical or electromagnetic field signals (currents and voltages [19], [20], [21], and instantaneous, active and reactive power, and external stray flux [22], [23], [24] or internal airgap flux [25], [26], [27], [28]), mechanical signals (mainly vibration [29] and noise) or eventually thermal signals (either temperature measurements or thermography) through different time-, frequency- or time-frequency domain processing techniques. Signal-based methods based on current and voltage, airgap flux and stray flux analysis are the most common. These are compared in Table I.

The most popular signal-based processing techniques category is spectral analysis, being the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) allowing to move from time to frequency domain, the most widespread technique under this category. For example, in a well-known reference for field winding ITF detection in BSM [19], the FFT is applied and signatures of the 3rd harmonic of the positive-sequence current are used for fault detection, while in other alternative works [29], the FFT is applied to analyze mechanical signals, such as vibrations.

Finally, there exist scarcer references for BSM modelling [30], [31], which is a necessary step for further model-based fault detection techniques [32]. In this regard, model-based techniques are hypothesized to be more accurate for protection purposes.

In a reference close to the present work [33] BSM rotor ITF detection criteria were suggested, based on the relation between the field current variation and the reactive power variation.

B. Shifting to Machine Learning

The field current in synchronous machines is a significant parameter of which continuous monitoring can ensure smooth

operation. Parameters characterizing a synchronous machine, are complex, highly coupled and non-linear [34], thus modelling for diagnosis purposes through analytical techniques is not an easy task, especially in the case of BSM. Therefore, shifting to data-driven, and more specifically artificial intelligence modelling, which represents a more convenient approach and which can lead to more accurate results, is nowadays a major trend.

The application of the analytical method proposed in [16] needs numerous prior tests of the machine under healthy conditions so as to obtain the no-load saturation curve, sustained short-circuit characteristic and also the value of Potier reactance, for which either full-load current at zero power factor test or extracted rotor test are required. This is unpractical in industry as it entails placing the machine out of service for testing.

Firstly, some work has been carried out regarding optimal tuning of multiple linear regression models for excitation current estimation in synchronous machines [35]. Although linear approximations are usually within acceptable limits in general, these solutions are deemed insufficient for high efficiency applications [34]. In [36], a further alternative hybrid technique is developed, applying metaheuristic methods under linear and quadratic relationships.

Beyond these linear approximations, data-driven solutions for electrical machine diagnosis [37] represent a notable research trend. Machine learning approaches have demonstrated to be excellent data-driven solutions to carry out estimations [38] and diagnostics [39], [40]. In particular, data-driven diagnostics of ITF in the field winding of salient pole synchronous generators was performed with great success in [41], through air-gap flux spectral density feature extraction and several machine learning classifiers training.

In the following, data-driven learning methods will be tackled specifically for field winding current estimation purpose in synchronous machines.

Supervised machine learning approaches have been developed for excitation current estimation in synchronous machines. In the research carried out in [42], a genetic algorithm-based k-nearest neighbor (KNN) estimator is implemented with fair results: 4.5% estimation error rate and 1.5% standard deviation. Moreover, in other works [43], reactive power compensation is performed by using the KNN classifier, attaining 3.98% mean absolute percentage error and 3.78% normalized root mean square error.

Also, under the category of supervised machine learning approaches, in [11] a support vector machine (SVM) algorithm is employed to estimate the exciter field current, with the aim of computing rotor ITF severity in synchronous machines with static excitation. This mathematical model is created from a multitude of operating data of the machine. The parameters of the model are adapted with the training data, faithfully representing the behavior of the machine in the range of the training data. Among the compared analytical methods (Potier and ASA) and the SVM method, the later performed the best with 0.448 mean average error and 0.009 root mean square error.

In other notable works, artificial neural networks (ANN) have been employed in synchronous machines for forward estimation (machine output estimation) [44] and for reverse estimation (excitation current estimation). Regarding reverse estimation, in

Fig. 1. Simplified layout of the field winding ITF detection and severity estimation technique (the rotating elements are contained in the gray area).

[45] less nodes were needed in comparison with ordinary ANN attaining 3.50% average error and 2.31% arithmetic average of all error rates. Regarding power factor compensation aims such as in [43], ANN-based techniques using dynamic reactive power compensators have also been introduced [46], [47], with good results in terms of accuracy, reliability, simplicity and fast computation.

III. FOUNDATIONS OF THE FAULT DETECTION AND SEVERITY ESTIMATION TECHNIQUE

This paper presents a novel field winding ITF detection and severity estimation technique in BSM through deep learning algorithms. Fig. 1 shows a simplified layout of the proposed method.

Firstly, machine output values are measured. In Fig. 1, phase voltages (U_A , U_B and U_C) and currents (I_A , I_B and I_C) are measured, although other combinations of phase or line measurements are possible. Consecutively, the theoretical exciter field current ($I_{e,cal}$) is computed through an artificial DNN model under healthy winding condition, purposefully developed as per Section IV. Finally, $I_{e,cal}$ is compared with the measured exciter field current ($I_{e,mea}$). The exciter field current estimation and the comparison are carried out online without need of other than the mentioned electrical measurements.

In order to avoid false tripping due to transients (start-up, shutdown, sudden load change, electromagnetic transients like pole slips, etc.), an adjustable time delay parameter (Δt) shall be added, so as only if the difference between $I_{e,cal}$ and $I_{e,mea}$ persists during this time the output signal is given out.

In the case of field winding ITF, the number of active turns is reduced. The fault severity level (α) is defined according to (1), regarding the number of faulty turns (N_{Fail}) with respect to the total number of turns (N_{Total}). In order to maintain the same magnetomotive force, the automatic voltage regulator (AVR) increases the field current ($I_{e,cal} < I_{e,mea}$) in proportion to the fault severity level. Therefore, the severity level is directly tied to the ratio between $I_{e,cal}$ and $I_{e,mea}$ as shown in (1).

$$\alpha [\%] = \frac{N_{Fail}}{N_{Total}} \cdot 100 = \left(1 - \frac{I_{e,cal}}{I_{e,mea}}\right) \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

If the proposed method is compared with previous analytical model-based exciter field current estimation techniques in BSM [16], employing the ASA method, the adverse effects of the

Fig. 2. DNN model development schema.

instrument transformers accuracy (voltage and current transformers), the measurement devices accuracy and the machine model accuracy itself on the estimation precision are overcome.

Specifically, as aforementioned, the machine model used to estimate the theoretical exciter excitation current from the measured active power, reactive power and output voltage relies on the knowledge of several machine electrical parameters, notably the Potier reactance and the short-circuit and no-load characteristic curves. The major disadvantage of this method is the difficult availability of the Potier reactance value, which requires to perform some special, costly and rarely performed tests such as the zero-power factor test at rated current.

The transition from analytical model-based excitation current techniques to new artificial intelligence methods has been experienced in the past with successful results in the case of synchronous machines with static excitation systems [11]. In that case, the accuracy was improved using SVM, so ITF at lower load conditions or with lower sensibility levels were made detectable.

In the case of BSM, the model-based estimation technique employed at an earlier stage [16] is even more complex giving place to even lower sensitivity, as two different machines are linked. The transition from this analytical model-based estimation technique to a new artificial intelligence method is hereby proposed using ANN, specifically DNN). The main advantage of DNN with respect to other algorithms such as SVM is the accuracy of the results. Other algorithms are an adequate solution when the quantity of available data is small, but with a large amount of data, it is recommended to use DNN to get a much more accurate model.

IV. APPLICATION OF DNN TO EXCITER FIELD CURRENT PREDICTION UNDER HEALTHY CONDITIONS

This paper proposes the use of deep learning algorithms to predict the value of the theoretical exciter field current in BSM, with the final aim of detecting ITF at the main machine field winding and given the case, of estimating its severity.

The exciter field current estimation is proposed through ANN, which is nowadays a trendy computational modeling technique. Deep ANN architectures (DNN), i.e., networks with multiple hidden layers, are able to adaptively model more complex relationships, from the defined inputs (in this case, U , P and Q , i.e., output phase voltage, active power and reactive power, respectively), through approximation of non-linear functions with a small error. The development of a DNN model is synthesized in Fig. 2.

There are infinite possibilities for the configuration of There are infinite possibilities for the configuration of DNNs, and

Fig. 3. DNN proposed architecture.

this will depend mainly on the complexity of the problem to be solved. The complexity of the problem is related mostly to the number of inputs and outputs of the DNN (the greater the number, the greater the amount of layers and neurons in each of the layers). In this case, the input layer of the DNN is consequently composed by three neurons, one for each of the inputs (U , P and Q). On the other hand, the DNN includes only one output neuron, with its activation function called F (sigmoid function).

With these three input variables and the output variable, a DNN with two hidden layers was built, under computational efficiency criteria. For each neuron of the first hidden layer, the activation functions (rectified linear unit, ReLU function) are called h_{1j} , with j representing the number of the neuron in the layer (j from 1 to J). For each neuron of the second hidden layer, the activation functions (ReLU function) are called h_{2k} , with k representing the number of the neuron in the layer (k from 1 to K). The DNN architecture is presented in Fig. 3.

Regarding hyperparameters, to define the optimal number of neurons in each hidden layer (J and K), the developments included training the DNN with all possible combinations of neurons in each of the two layers, from 3 to 20 neurons in each of the layers, using backpropagation. Also, in this training process the learning rate for the backpropagation process (l) was fixed at 0.001, and the number of epochs (T) was fixed at 40.000. Then, to choose the optimal configuration among all, with which to pursue the work, the trained DNNs were evaluated under minimization of the root mean square error (RMSE) and of the number of points with errors greater than 5%.

In the following, the main features of the DNN development stages are described.

A. Data Collection and Processing

First and foremost, an initial data pool was obtained through experimental testing on a special laboratory testbench, described in Section V, under healthy machine conditions. This data pool was obtained by performing 9 different tests series, each of them at different grid voltage values around the rated voltage (400 V), from 380 V to 420 V with 5 V steps.

Each series was composed by 14 repetitions, each of them with different constant mechanical power input from the prime mover, so as to cover the whole active power test range ($0 \leq P$

Fig. 4. Operating region and data points considered for DNN model development.

≤ 3000 W), swiping the whole reactive power test range from under-excited to over-excited conditions ($-2000 \leq Q \leq 3000$ var) through incremental steps applied on the excitation power provision.

The operating region subjected to testing, defined by $[380 \leq U \leq 420$ V], $[0 \leq P \leq 3000$ W] and $[-2000 \leq Q \leq 3000$ var], is shown in Fig. 4.

This step is vital because the quality of the gathered data is directly related to the quality of the final model.

Once the measurements were obtained, filtering of anomalous data, including transients, is required. Notably the measurements exceeding the predefined value range shown in and the ones appertaining to a 2% upper and lower boundary layers of active and reactive power values were neglected.

The initial data set is composed by 7403607 measurements, and after the filtering process, the measurements used to train the DNN are 7035463 (4.97%).

After refining the initial data pool, it is divided into three different data sets under random sampling: training set (accounting for 70% of the initial data pool), validation set (accounting for 15%) and test set (accounting for the remaining 15%).

B. Training With Validation

The DNN is trained under a progressive weight adjustment process known as backpropagation. The training process consists in the DNN adjusting the value of its internal weights to bring closer the outputs ($I_{e,cal}$) to the measured values ($I_{e,mea}$).

Firstly, at each epoch, for each input signals (U , P and Q), these are propagated forward through the synaptic connections until an output signal is generated ($I_{e,cal}$). The overall feed-forward propagation can be expressed as:

$$I_{e,cal} = F \left[\sum_{k=1}^K w_{F,2k} h_{2k} \left(\sum_{j=1}^J w_{2k,1j} h_{1j} (w_{1j,U} \cdot U + w_{1j,P} \cdot P + w_{1j,Q} \cdot Q + w_{j,0}) + w_{k,0} \right) + w_{F,0} \right] \quad (2)$$

where $w_{F,2k}$ represents the synaptic weights of each connection from the neurons of the second hidden layer to the output neuron, $w_{2k,1j}$ represents the synaptic weights of the connections among the neurons of the first hidden layer to the ones of the second hidden layer, and $w_{1j,U}$, $w_{1j,P}$ and $w_{1j,Q}$ represent the synaptic weights of the connections of the neurons of the input layer to the ones of the first hidden layer, and where $w_{F,0}$, $w_{K,0}$ and $w_{J,0}$ represent the neuron bias values applied to the neurons of the output layer, the second hidden layer and the first hidden layer, respectively.

From here on, the weights vector will be written as:

$$W^t = [w_{F,2k} \ w_{2k,1j} \ w_{1j,U} \ w_{1j,P} \ w_{1j,Q}] \quad (3)$$

with j from 1 to J , and k from 1 to K .

Secondly, after the feed-forward propagation stage, the error signals between the estimated values ($I_{e,cal}$) and the desired values ($I_{e,mea}$) are computed. The prediction error process employed is based on iteratively updating the synaptic weights, so the mean square error of the N measurements serves as an adequate cost function (CF) to be minimized:

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{\{W\}} [CF] \quad (4)$$

$$CF = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (I_{e,cal} - I_{e,mea})^2 \quad (5)$$

Consecutively, the error signal is propagated backwards through the network in order to adjust the weights and to progressively minimize the CF. The Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam) algorithm is employed as the descent-gradient optimization method. The optimizer uses the exponential moving average of the gradient (first momentum, ∇CF) and squared-gradient (second momentum, $(\nabla CF)^2$), for which the partial derivatives of the CF with respect to each of the weights are computed.

The general expression that allows to update the weights vector at epoch t (W_t) from the weights vector at the former epoch $t-1$ (W_{t-1}) moving towards the negative direction of the gradient, has the following form:

$$W_t = W_{t-1} - l \cdot \frac{\hat{m}_t}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_t + \varepsilon}} \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{m}_t = m_t \cdot \frac{1}{1 - \beta_m} \quad (7)$$

$$m_t = \beta_m \cdot m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_m) \cdot \nabla CF \quad (8)$$

$$\hat{v}_t = v_t \cdot \frac{1}{1 - \beta_v} \quad (9)$$

$$v_t = \beta_v \cdot v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_v) \cdot (\nabla CF)^2 \quad (10)$$

where l represents the learning rate that allows to speed up the convergence of the CF to its minimum and ε , β_m and β_v are constant.

Once the DNN has gone through the training process, the validation process is applied to several outcoming networks. At this stage, hyperparameter tuning of the model is performed to choose the best fitting network. To do so, the mean squared error obtained with each of the trained networks is again used as the function to minimize. For similar mean squared errors, the

Fig. 5. Calculated excitation current (red) and measured excitation current (blue) under machine healthy conditions.

Fig. 6. Calculated error of the neural network model in healthy conditions.

tiebreak is the minimization of the number of points for which an absolute error is greater than 5%. Therefore, both the absolute deviations from zero (dispersion) and the overall closeness to mean zero are considered.

Several open-source libraries have been used to build the code: Pandas to work with dataframes, Numpy to work with numerical arrays and Keras regarding all resources related to ANN.

C. Test

A final unbiased evaluation of the performance of the chosen algorithm to predict the exciter field current under healthy conditions is carried out, after the training and validation process.

Fig. 5 shows the measured excitation current (in blue) and the calculated excitation current (in red). In Fig. 6, it is shown the calculated error of the neural network evaluating data of the machine in healthy conditions. As it can be seen, the maximum absolute error is around 1%, so the neural network model can detect ITF with a severity greater than 1%.

It shall be noted that abscissa in both Figs. 5 and 6 is represented in increasing order of exciter field current. All the measurement points contained in the experimental dataset under healthy conditions are included in these figures.

Table II shows the main mathematical metrics of the DNN accuracy evaluation under healthy conditions. The errors obtained through DNN prediction are sensibly lower than the errors obtained in previous works employing analytical techniques [34].

TABLE II
RESULTS OBTAINED FROM NEURAL NETWORK PREDICTIONS UNDER HEALTHY CONDITIONS

Set of data	MAE [mA]	RMSE [mA]	MAPE [%]	SMAPE [%]
Tests under Healthy Conditions	0.05	0.06	0.57	0.59

A mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.05 shows that the trained DNN is a highly accurate and faithful mathematical model to represent the behavior of the BSM in terms of excitation current requirement. On the other hand, the root mean square error (RMSE) is more sensitive to outliers or large errors, therefore a RMSE of 0.06 represents a fair mean prediction dispersion value.

Regarding percentual metrics, a mean absolute percentual error (MAPE) of 0.57% and a symmetrical mean average percentual error (SMAPE) of 0.59 puts forward that the neural network predictions are really good. But it is important to notice that for this application the best metric to evaluate the accurate of the neural network is the RMSE, because minimizing this metric it has been minimizing the number of points with large predictions deviations.

A notable improvement is observed if the errors obtained in the prediction through DNN are compared with previous theoretical model-based methods employing well-known standard methods such as Potier or ASA, with relative errors analogous to MAPE up to 6% [16]. This implies that the accuracy has been improved by 6 with respect to this benchmark, enabling to detect much less severe ITF with total certainty, i.e., faults with 1% or more shorted turns would be detectable. Note that because 1% of shorted turns is the less severe detectable fault, tripping threshold may never be fixed at a lower value.

Also, these metrics results shall be interpreted hand in hand with the precision (accuracy class) of the instrumentation transformers and the measurement devices used to acquire the required inputs for the excitation current estimation. In typical industrial applications, with 0.5 accuracy class voltage transformers (0.5% admissible error between 80% and 120% of its rated voltage), 0.5 accuracy class current transformers (1.5% admissible error at 5% of its rated load according to standards) and an ordinary 0.5% error related to programmable transducers, the prediction accuracy provided by the DNN is very reasonable.

V. EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

A. Experimental Setup

Numerous tests under healthy condition and under different rotor ITF severity levels were performed on a 4-salient pole 5 kVA, 400 V, BSM. This machine has been modified to enable access to the field winding of the main machine and to the rotating diodes, to perform faults. A simplified diagram of the machine is shown in the Fig. 7.

For these purposes five slip rings and brushes have been added. The diodes are placed out of the machine. Moreover, the connections between poles are accessible through three terminals

Fig. 7. Experimental setup simplified diagram.

Fig. 8. Experimental setup: 1; main machine, 2; exciter, 3; diodes, 4; resistor connection in parallel with one pole, 5; slip rings and brushes, and 6; driver (induction motor).

installed at the rotor. In this way it is possible to perform ITF at the field winding of the main machine between poles number 2 or 3.

The values of stator voltage (U), active power (P) and reactive power (Q) are measured by a commercial 3 channel programable transducer. The exciter field current is measured by a Hall effect sensor. The four variables are recorded on the computer through an Arduino © microcontroller.

The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 8. The main machine (1) and the exciter (2) have a common frame. The diodes (3) which are normally installed in the rotor, in this arrangement are placed out of the machine. Moreover, the poles connections (3) are accessible through three terminals installed on the shaft of the machine. There are five slip rings and brushes (5), three of them connected to the armature winding of the exciter and the other two connected to the main machine field winding. This modified BSM is driven by an induction motor (6) controlled through a variable frequency converter. Excitation power to the BSM is provided through a variable DC source. The BSM is connected to the grid through a variable auto-transformer in order to adjust the grid voltage.

TABLE III
MAIN MACHINE DATA

Synchronous 3-phase	
Alternator Type	Synchronous 3-phase
Rated Power	5 kVA
Rated Speed	1500 rpm
Rated Voltage	400 V
Rated Current	7.2 A
Pole pairs	2
Rated Frequency	50 Hz
IP	21
Isolation Class	F
Rated Excitation Voltage	33 V
Rated Excitation Current	4.10 A

TABLE IV
EXCITER DATA

Synchronous 3-phase	
Alternator Type	Synchronous 3-phase
Rated Power	277 VA
Rated Speed	1500 rpm
Rated Voltage	40 V
Rated Current	4 A
Pole pairs	4
Rated Frequency	100 Hz
IP	21
Isolation Class	F
Rated Excitation Voltage	33 V
Rated Excitation Current	0.61 A

TABLE V
SETS OF FAULTY TESTS PERFORMED AT THE LABORATORY

Set no.	$R_f [\Omega]$	$\alpha [\%]$
1	0.08	24
2	3.71	8.75
3	8.87	4.60
4	1000	0.05

Detailed data on the main synchronous machine and on the exciter is provided in Tables III and IV respectively.

B. Experimental Faulty Tests

Four sets of faulty winding condition tests have been performed to validate the proposed method, which relies on the DNN model developed to estimate the exciter field current from the output values. These tests consist of simulating the existence of an ITF at the field winding of the main machine with four different severity levels.

This faulty effect is achieved at the laboratory by connecting a known value resistor in parallel with a rotor pole. The effect of an ITF and the connection of a parallel resistor is the same as both are reflected in an increase in the value of the excitation current for the same machine operating point.

The severity of the ITF is related to the value of the resistor connected in parallel to one of the rotor poles (R_f), given a total rotor resistance value of 8.05 Ω .

As mentioned before, the tests were carried out for four different parallel resistance values, simulating several short-circuited turns in each case, as shown in Table V.

For each test, measurements of stator voltage (U), active power (P), reactive power (Q), and excitation current ($I_{e,mea}$) are taken. Then, in each case, the proposed method is applied as per Section III, for which the previously trained DNN is applied to the obtained output measurements.

In case of ITF, the DNN model for each measured operating point will predict a lower value of the excitation current than the measured one ($I_{e,cal} < I_{e,mea}$). At each point the predicted or theoretical excitation current value and the real or measured excitation current value shall be compared. With the difference between these two excitation currents, the number of shorted turns, i.e., the fault severity level, can be estimated through (1).

If for each test, the estimation of short-circuited turns attained through the DNN model previously trained with the machine under healthy conditions and the actual number of short-circuited turns match, then the developed method will be fully valid for use in this application. This evaluation is carried out in Section VI.

VI. RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED TECHNIQUE FOR FIELD WINDING INTER-TURN FAULT SEVERITY ESTIMATION

For each of the four sets of faulty winding condition experimental tests described in Section V, the results have been analyzed. The proposed method has been applied to faulty test sets 1 to 4. For each set of faulty tests, the results have been summarized in two graphics.

The first graphic for each test set shows the measured excitation current (in blue) and the calculated excitation current (in red) for all the experimental data points, with increasing exciter field current order criteria in abscissa. The calculated excitation current value is calculated through the DNN previously trained with the machine operational data under healthy conditions.

As it can be seen in these graphics (Figs. 9, 11, 13 and 15), the higher the value of the parallel resistance, the lower the simulated fault severity, and therefore the lower the difference between the measured excitation current and the calculated excitation current through the DNN model.

The second graphic for each test shows the calculated fault severity (Figs. 10, 12, 14 and 16), in terms of ratio of shorted turns, with increasing exciter field current order criteria in abscissa. Given the measured excitation current and the calculated or theoretical excitation current, the severity of the ITF is estimated through (1).

It is important to notice that during these faulty tests the value of the parallel resistance is not controlled, therefore its value naturally varies as the BSM runs at higher load due to temperature increase. This explains why the calculated value of the ITF severity is not constant during each set of tests. Because of this fact, in order to evaluate the optimal performance of the DNN, the real value of the ITF severity is compared with the mean value of the calculated ITF severity.

The results for the different severity levels are summarized in Table VI. The results displayed in this table show how the DNN trained with healthy operating data allows to estimate with a high accuracy the severity of ITF. Nevertheless, it should be noted that for less than 1% of short-circuited turns, which is the accuracy security level of the healthy exciter field current prediction algorithm, the fault severity estimation is less accurate, such as in set no. 4. Such subtle ITF close to healthy conditions lead to greater estimation errors. Therefore, in order to avoid false tripping, α shall be only considered when greater than 1%.

TABLE VI
RESULTS OF THE EVALUATION OF NEURAL NETWORK ON THE ESTIMATION OF THE ITF SEVERITY

Set no.	R_f [Ω]	Real α [%]	Estimated mean α [%]	Error in estimation [%]
1	0.08	24	24.63	0.63
2	3.71	8.75	8.60	0.15
3	8.87	4.60	4.71	0.11
4	1000	0.05	0.04	0.01

A. Set no. 1 ($R_f = 0.08 \Omega$)

Fig. 9. Measured (blue) and calculated (red) excitation currents ($R_f = 0.08 \Omega$).

Fig. 10. Calculated ITF severity ($R_f = 0.08 \Omega$).

B. Set no. 2 ($R_f = 3.71 \Omega$)

Fig. 11. Measured (blue) and calculated (red) excitation currents ($R_f = 3.71 \Omega$).

Fig. 12. Calculated ITF severity ($R_f = 3.71 \Omega$).

C. Set no. 3 ($R_f = 8.87 \Omega$)

Fig. 13. Measured (blue) and calculated (red) excitation currents ($R_f = 8.87 \Omega$).

Fig. 14. Calculated ITF severity ($R_f = 8.87 \Omega$).

D. Set no. 4 ($R_f = 1000 \Omega$)

Fig. 15. Measured (blue) and calculated (red) excitation currents ($R_f = 1000 \Omega$).

Fig. 16. Calculated ITF severity ($R_f = 1000 \Omega$).

VII. CONCLUSION

ITF at the main machine field winding in BSM are prospective electrical faults. These are not easy to detect given the scarcity of achievable measurements in the rotating elements. Nowadays, there are many methods to detect ITF. Most of them are signal-based, consisting in processing electrical or electromagnetic, mechanical or thermal signals through different time-, frequency- or time-frequency domain processing techniques. Signal-based methods based on current and voltage, airgap flux and stray flux analysis are the most common. The main problems of these methods are their cost and accuracy.

In this paper an ITF online model-based detection and fault severity estimation algorithm for BSM is proposed. This algorithm relies on a DNN trained with numerous machine healthy operation points obtained experimentally.

The trained DNN can predict the exciter field current requirement of the machine under healthy conditions from the measurements of stator voltage, active power and reactive power acquired at the machine output. Then, the method suggests comparing the predicted excitation current with the measured excitation current. From this comparison, ITF can be detected and its severity can be computed.

The results of the training process show that the DNN can predict the value of the excitation current of the BSM with an average error of 1%. So, it shall be able to estimate ITF with a fault severity greater than 1% with all certainty.

This entails a cut-down by 6 in terms of accuracy with respect to previous analytical model-based methods, joint to the avoidance of performing costly off-line tests on the machine in order to obtain the required theoretical model parameters.

To validate the operation of the proposed method in real cases, an experimental testbench has been set up to simulate ITF with different severity levels at the field winding of a BSM.

The developed method could be extended to large size industrial machines if DNN training under normal conditions is carried out after commissioning. Also, the method could be extended to the detection of ITF in synchronous machines with other excitation systems and to the detection of other types of electrical faults in the excitation system that have a similar effect of increasing the excitation power requirement, including exciter faults and rotating rectifier faults.

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